

Galactic Center Newsletter

IAUS405: Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time, Brno (<https://gc2026.muni.cz/>)

Vol. XXIX / No. 2

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF: Václav Pavlík — EDITORIAL BOARD: Vladimír Karas, Petra Suková, and Maitrayee Gupta

May 19, 2026

EDITORIAL: THE ABBOT OF BRNO CULTIVATING THE FOUNDATIONS OF MODERN GENEALOGY

By MAITRAYEE GUPTA

Gregor Mendel (20 July 1822 – 6 January 1884) was best known in his time as an Augustinian friar and the Abbot of St. Thomas' Abbey in Brno, but is today recognized as the father of modern genetics. His work forms the basis of our understanding of heredity, which is to say the way that specific traits are passed from parent to child.

Born to a peasant family in Heinzendorf bei Odrau (modern Hynčice), Mendel was recognized from a young age as uncommonly intelligent and was educated in Tropolau

Statue of Gregor Mendel at St. Thomas' Abbey in Brno

(modern Opava), graduating in 1840. From there, he studied for a further three years at the Philosophical Institute of the University of Olmutz, excelling in mathematics and physics and deciding to pursue a career that combined his love of science with his Christian upbringing. So it was that at the age of 22, he became a monk of the Augustinian order at St. Thomas' Abbey, which was home to scientists of many disciplines at the time. The abbot of his admission, Franz Cyril Napp, was himself a botanist and would be a highly important figure in the rest of Mendel's life.

Mendel was ordained as a priest in 1847, but, as his talents were better suited to science than to the ministry, Abbot Napp recommended that he continue his studies at the Royal Imperial University in Vienna. There, he studied physics and botany alongside his contemporaries Christian Doppler and Franz Unger, respectively, developing the skills he would later use for the experiments that defined his legacy.

Between 1856 and 1863, at the abbey in Brno, Mendel conducted his now-famous experiments with peas, cultivating some 28,000 plants to record the effects of cross-pollinating and hybridizing them. He observed the way that traits such as height, pod colour, and seed shape were passed from one generation of plants to the next. When two plants with purebred versions of a trait were crossbred, creating hybrids, those hybrids would then, when self-pollinating, produce offspring with that trait at a ratio of 3:1 (three plants in four exhibited the dominant version of the trait and one showed the recessive version). We now call these the dominant and recessive alleles of a gene. This work was compiled in his seminal paper *Experiments in Plant Hybridization* [1, 2], published in 1866. Two years later, Mendel was elected

to the position of Abbot upon the death of Abbot Napp, demonstrating the high esteem in which his colleagues held him. He would hold the position until his death in 1884, continuing to pursue science, including apiculture, founding the Austrian Meteorological Society, and hybridization experiments with other plants.

While *Experiments in Plant Hybridization* was distributed in a limited fashion in the 19th century, it would not be until over a decade after Mendel's death that his contributions would be fully recognized. After 1900, independent studies began to reproduce Mendel's results and identify his work as the primary published source. Hence, Mendelian genetics was born. While initially a hotly debated topic in the first two decades of the 20th century, it eventually gained acceptance and became both the bedrock of modern genetics and part of the basis for evolutionary biology. Mendel himself is immortalized in Brno with a statue in the courtyard of the abbey that nurtured his talent and his work. ■

- [1] G. Mendel. *Verhandlungen des naturforschenden Vereines in Brünn* 4 (1866), 3–47.
- [2] S. Abbott and D. J. Fairbanks. *Genetics* **204.2** (2016), 407–422.

Example pea flower hybridization experiment showing the principles of Mendelian genetics

MACHIAN EFFECTS NEAR BLACK HOLES

By VLADIMÍR KARAS

Ernst Mach was born in 1838 in Chrlice (now part of Brno), and this year marks the 110th anniversary of his death. A commemorative plaque can be found on the native house of Ernst Mach, just a few miles from our conference venue. As a renowned physicist, Mach influenced Albert Einstein, together with entire generations of his followers (as well as opponents) across diverse branches of physics and philosophy. For almost three decades, Mach held the chair of experimental physics at Charles–Ferdinand University in Prague; in 1871, he was elected a member of the Royal Bohemian Society of Sciences. To the participants of the ongoing IAU Symposium 405, the geographical association with nearby cities of Prague, Vienna, and Graz is not the only point of interest.

We can readily identify multiple directions of Mach’s scientific research. Let us mention just two of them, which are closely linked to the discussion during our Meeting.

On Mach number. In 1887, Ernst Mach and Peter Salcher presented their description of the sound effects observed during the supersonic motion of a projectile. They discovered the origin and the basic properties of a conical shock wave induced by a moving body. In fact, for the first time, the method of *shadowgraph* was successfully employed to visualize the flow passing around a supersonic object [1]. This has allowed the

measurements of bow-shock parameters. In several talks presented during the Symposium, we notice how the stars, as hugely scaled-up bullets, roar at supersonic speeds through the gaseous environment of the Galactic Center and the winds emanating from other stars, thereby creating shock waves analogous to those explored by Mach. People discuss not only how bow-shock structures formed by stars colliding with an outflow from the Galactic Centre, but also the effect of ablation that changes these gaseous “projectiles”. The outflow density and the velocity can be constrained through the shock characteristics in perfect reminiscences of Mach’s study of the projectiles in his laboratory.

On Mach’s Principle. Closer towards the borderline area between theoretical physics and philosophy stands the conjecture in which Mach has attempted to relate the motion of distant stars to the local inertial frames; more broadly, to connect the origin of inertia and the local physical laws with the large-scale structure of the Universe. This concept guided Albert Einstein during the development of the General Theory of Relativity, although it is only indirectly implemented in its mathematical formulation via the tensor calculus. In the end, the influence of Mach’s principle was suppressed with time in Einstein’s considerations, but it has never disappeared [2]. In the contemporary works, we can see the realization of the idea in the action of relativistic frame-dragging to which *nothing* can resist in the sphere of ergoregion. Not only are particles and fluids forced to co-rotate with the black

Magnetic lines of force form critical points as they are distorted by the rotation of the black hole (credit: Karas et al. [3])

hole, but also fields are dragged and field lines distorted. In the context of a supermassive black hole in Sgr A*, the Machian frame-dragging has been introduced as a geometrical foundation of the magnetic field reconnections that can accelerate matter to very high energy at the expense of black hole rotation.

“When the subway jerks, it’s the fixed stars that throw you down.”
— Phillip Frank

Phillip Frank, an elite theoretical physicist and the successor to Einstein at Prague University, as a member of the eminent *Vienna Circle*, influenced 20th-century philosophy profoundly [4]. When lecturing on Mach’s principle to students at Harvard University, Frank allegedly attributed the quote above to Mach himself. While Brno still awaits the construction of its first metro transportation line, the example invokes the association of the Principle with one of its leading attributes: the local impact of inertial effects due to distant stars cannot be shielded even by the mass of intervening bodies. ■

Ernst Waldfried Josef Wenzel Mach (Zeitschr. f. Phys. Chemie, 40, 1902) Historical shadowgraph of shock waves around a bullet in supersonic motion (taken in Prague, 1888)

- [1] P. Mach and Salcher. *Annalen der Physik und Chemie* (1887), 277–291.
- [2] J. B. Barbour. “Einstein and his interpretation of Mach’s principle”. *Ernst Mach and the Development of Physics*. Ed. by V. Prosser and J. Folta. Prague: Charles University, 1988, 67–82.
- [3] V. Karas, O. Kopáček, and D. Kunneriath. *Classical and Quantum Gravity* **29.3**, (2012), 035010.
- [4] P. Frank. *Philosophy of Science: The Link Between Science and Philosophy*. Reprinted by Dover Publications, New York, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1957.

HORIZON-SCALE IMAGING OF SAGITTARIUS A*

By EVENT HORIZON TELESCOPE
COLLABORATION

Sgr A*: a black hole at the Galactic Centre

Sagittarius A* (Sgr A*), the compact radio source at the centre of the Milky Way, marks the position of the nearest supermassive black hole and provides a unique laboratory for exploring gravity and plasma physics in the strong-field regime. Its mass, $M \approx 4.1 \times 10^6 M_\odot$, and distance, $d \approx 8.1$ kpc, have been determined with high precision through decades of monitoring of stellar orbits in the Galactic Centre [1, 2]. On horizon scales, the expected observational signature is a ring formed by light emitted from accreting plasma that is lensed in the black hole's gravitational potential, surrounding a central dark region associated with the shadow. Given the mass and distance to Sgr A*, the critical curve bounding the shadow is expected to subtend an angular diameter of about $52 \mu\text{as}$, corresponding to a projected gravitational radius $r_g/D \approx 5 \mu\text{as}$, where $r_g \equiv GM/c^2$. Resolving structures on this scale requires angular resolutions far beyond those achievable with conventional telescopes.

The Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) is a global very-long-baseline interferometric array operating at millimetre wavelengths that combines radio telescopes distributed across the Earth to form an Earth-sized virtual telescope. Observing at 1.3 mm (230 GHz), the array achieves angular resolutions of order $20 \mu\text{as}$, sufficient to resolve the shadow created by the black hole in Sgr A* [3].

Imaging a rapidly variable source

The first EHT observations of Sgr A* suitable for imaging were obtained during the 2017 observing campaign, when M87*, a much more massive black hole ($6.5 \times 10^9 M_\odot$), was also observed. Compared to the case of M87*, imaging the Galactic Centre black hole presents unique challenges. Because of its much smaller mass, the dynamical timescales of plasma near the event horizon are extremely short: orbital periods near the innermost stable circular orbit are of order

tens of minutes. As a consequence, the emission structure of Sgr A* is expected to evolve significantly during a typical VLBI observing track. In addition to intrinsic variability, observations toward the Galactic Centre are affected by strong interstellar scattering caused by turbulent ionized plasma along the line of sight. Although scattering decreases at millimetre wavelengths, its residual effects must still be modelled and mitigated during the imaging process.

To address these challenges, the EHT analysis combined reliable interferometric observables with extensive synthetic-data validation and multiple independent imaging pipelines, ensuring that the recovered structures remain stable against methodological assumptions and systematic uncertainties. In particular, the analysis relied heavily on closure quantities, which are robust to station-based calibration errors, enabling the extraction of structural information even in the presence of significant source variability and sparse interferometric coverage.

The first horizon-scale image

In 2022, the EHT collaboration reported the first horizon-scale image of Sgr A*, shown in the top figure [4]. Despite the intrinsic variability of the source, independent imaging methods consistently recover a ring-like emission structure. Because the characteristic dynamical timescale near the event horizon is of order minutes, the published image should be interpreted as a representation of the characteristic spatial scale of the emission rather than a snapshot of the instantaneous structure of the accretion flow. The diameter of this ring is $51.8 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{as}$, in excellent agreement with theoretical expectations for the gravitationally lensed emission produced by plasma orbiting near a black hole with the mass and distance inferred from stellar dynamics. This shows, in particular, that the total mass of $4.1 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ constrained by stellar orbits to be contained within about 15 mas of Sgr A* (about 3,000 gravitational radii) is in fact confined to be within 5 gravitational radii. This arguably provides the most stringent constraint to date for the presence of a supermassive black hole at the centre of the Milky Way.

The ring morphology arises from strong gravitational lensing near the photon orbit. Photons emitted in the inner accretion flow can orbit the black hole before escaping to

Horizon-scale image of Sgr A* obtained by the EHT at 230 GHz. The observed ring-like morphology is consistent with gravitationally lensed emission produced by hot plasma orbiting near the event horizon of the Galactic Centre black hole.

ward the observer, producing a bright ring that traces the critical curve of the spacetime. Importantly, the size of this ring depends primarily on the spacetime geometry and only weakly on the detailed properties of the emitting plasma [5].

Accretion and plasma physics

Unlike the black hole in M87, whose large-scale emission is dominated by a powerful relativistic jet, Sgr A* is a comparatively low-luminosity accreting system. The millimetre emission detected by the EHT is thought to originate from hot electrons in a magnetized accretion flow located within only a few gravitational radii from the event horizon. Interpreting these observations is aided by comparison with general relativistic magnetohydrodynamic (GRMHD) simulations coupled with relativistic radiative transfer calculations. These models reliably reproduce the observed ring morphology, supporting a picture in which the emission arises from turbulent plasma in the inner accretion flow. At the same time, current observations do not match the characteristic time variability of GRMHD simulations, nor uniquely determine the detailed structure of the accretion flow [6]. Future observations will focus on narrowing the degeneracies among simulations with different initial assumptions, particularly regarding electron thermodynamics and magnetic field geometry.

The radio emission observed at the horizon scale is found to be highly polarized,

favoring MAD models where magnetic fields are dynamically important [7, 8]. However, ambiguities regarding the nature of the screen producing Faraday rotation along the line of sight prevent a definite interpretation of the time-variable polarized emission.

A new observational window on the Galactic Centre

The first EHT image of Sgr A* marks the beginning of a new observational capability in which the Galactic Centre black hole can be probed directly on horizon scales. An important next step will be the development of dynamic imaging approaches able to re-

construct the time-dependent structure of the emission. Such analyses aim to move beyond time-averaged reconstructions and directly probe the evolving plasma dynamics on horizon scales.

Future observations with improved sensitivity and expanded baseline coverage will enable higher-fidelity imaging and increasingly time-resolved studies of the accretion flow. Polarimetric measurements will provide new constraints on the magnetic field structure close to the event horizon, while dynamic imaging techniques may reveal evolving plasma structures on orbital timescales.

Combined with complementary probes such as stellar dynamics and future pulsar

timing experiments in the Galactic Centre, horizon-scale observations of Sgr A* will continue to play a central role in advancing our understanding of accretion physics, black holes, and gravity in the strong-field regime. ■

- [1] A. M. Ghez et al. *ApJ* **689.2** (2008), 1044–1062.
- [2] S. Gillessen et al. *ApJ* **692.2** (2009), 1075–1109.
- [3] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **875.1**, (2019), L2.
- [4] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **930.2**, (2022), L12.
- [5] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **930.2**, (2022), L17.
- [6] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **930.2**, (2022), L16.
- [7] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **964.2**, (2024), L25.
- [8] Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration et al. *ApJ* **964.2**, (2024), L25.

BRNO: FAR FROM THE GALACTIC CENTER, CLOSE TO THE CENTER OF THE UNIVERSE

By PETRA SUKOVÁ

For participants of a conference, the idea of a “center of the Universe” may sound pleasantly provocative. For much of history, however, it was taken quite seriously. In Aristotelian cosmology, Earth occupied the central position, and this picture survived well into the Middle Ages. The Copernican revolution displaced Earth from that role, but

it still kept alive the hope that the Universe might have some preferred center. Only with Newton, and later with figures not entirely foreign to the Czech lands — the abovementioned Ernst Mach, born near Brno and later active in Prague, and Albert Einstein, who also taught in Prague — did the notion of a privileged center gradually dissolve. In modern cosmology, there is no distinguished central point: on sufficiently large scales, the Universe has no unique center at all.

Brno, however, offers a charming local exception. Deep discussions about cosmology and the center of the Universe were once conducted by two young Czech scientists: Jiří Grygar (who became one of the

best-known Czech astronomers) and Alexander Ženíšek (later a physicist and mathematician), as they walked to and from their Gymnasium in Elgartova Street. They chose the street intersection, where they regularly met on their daily journeys, to represent Brno’s Center of the Universe. The story was later recalled by Zdeněk Mikulášek in the book *Sto astronomických omylů uvedených na pravou míru* (loosely translated as *One hundred*

astronomical misconceptions set straight) [1], written together with Zdeněk Horský and Zdeněk Pokorný. In 2019, the site even received its own playful memorial at the corner of Demlova and Trávníky streets (see the map). So while discussing the true center of our own Galaxy, conference participants may also wish to visit Brno’s unofficial – but perhaps best-loved – Center of the Universe, favored by Jiří Grygar and Alexander Ženíšek and located about an hour’s walk from the conference venue. ■

- [1] Z. Horský, Z. Mikulášek, and Z. Pokorný. *Sto astronomických omylů uvedených na pravou míru*. Czech. Praha: Svoboda, 1988.

“Center of the Universe is everywhere. This one is beloved by dr. Jiří Grygar and prof. Alexander Ženíšek. (2012)”

The location of Brno’s Center of the Universe. Interested readers may navigate there using the link <https://mapy.com/s/gujugehulo>.